

STUDIES IN THE PYRIDINE SERIES. PART II. A NEW SYNTHESIS OF 2-METHYL-4-ETHYLPYRIDINE.

BY RAFAT HUSAIN SIDDIQUI AND ABDUL QUDDUS KHAN.

The monostyryl base, obtained from 2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine, has been oxidised to 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine- α -carboxylic acid, which is decarboxylated to 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine. The picrate of the latter, m.p. 142° , on admixture with the picrate of $C_8H_{11}N$ obtained after alkaline degradation of strychnine and brucine, melts at 125° thus proving the non-identity of the latter with 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine.

In Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 410) of this series a synthesis of 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine was attempted by one of us (R.H.S.). By condensing 2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine and benzaldehyde in presence of zinc chloride an aldol condensation product, a distyryl and a monostyryl derivative have been obtained. In the present investigation acetic anhydride has been used instead of zinc chloride when the monostyryl (60%), the distyryl (25%) and some unreacted base (15%) have been isolated from the condensate and no trace of alkin is formed. The three bases have been separated *via* their salts (*vide* experimental). The distyryl hydrochloride is insoluble in water while the hydrochlorides of the monostyryl and the trialkyl base are easily soluble even in ice-cold water, the free bases being separated by distillation. After the removal of the trialkyl pyridine (b.p. $183-85^{\circ}$) the residue is distilled at $205^{\circ}/2$ mm. when the monostyryl derivative is obtained as a thick straw-coloured liquid. The base from distyryl hydrochloride crystallises from petroleum ether, m.p. 85° . The distyryl base does not condense with benzaldehyde further under the conditions tried. The monostyryl derivative (2-styryl-4-ethyl-6-methylpyridine) has been oxidised in acetone solution by means of potassium permanganate when benzoic acid and α -methyl- β -ethylpyridine- α' -carboxylic acid is obtained from the slimy precipitate while some unoxidised substance is recovered from the solvent. The α -carboxylic acid, on decarboxylation with a trace of copper powder, gives the desired base. This has been converted into a picrate, m.p. 142° . The m.p. of the picrate and its analytical values are in agreement with those given in literature for 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine. This picrate on admixture with the picrate of the base $C_8H_{11}N$, isolated from strychnine and brucine as a result of alkaline degradation, shows a marked depression.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2:6 Dimethyl-4-ethyl pyridine (Part I, *loc. cit.*) was further purified *via* the picrate and then regenerating it from the picrate.

Condensation of 2:6-Dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine with Benzaldehyde.—A mixture of the base (1 mol., 12 g.), freshly distilled benzaldehyde (1.05 mol., 9.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (12 g.) were gently refluxed for 14 hours. The dark coloured solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and distilled in steam to remove benzaldehyde. The residue was again treated with more hydrochloric acid when some crystals "B" imbedded in a pasty mass separated from the acid solution "A". The crystalline mass "B" was washed with a little dilute acetic acid. The pasty mass "C" was dissolved in chloroform and after removal of tarry impurities by addition of ether to the solution it crystallised in hexagonal needles which proved identical with "B" (mixed m. p.) and was the hydrochloride of the distyryl derivative. The pasty residue from chloroform solution "C" was converted into a picrate and is under examination. The aqueous acid mother-liquor after cooling at 0° overnight was filtered from traces of the hydrochloride "B". The clear yellow filtrate was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and shaken with petroleum ether. The petroleum ether solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and after removal of the solvent gave a straw-coloured thick oily base. The unreacted base (2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine), b.p. 180-86°, was removed and identified by conversion into the picrate (m.p. 120°). The residue distilled at 205°/2 mm. to a thick oily liquid and proved to be 2-styryl-4-ethyl-6-methylpyridine, by conversion into the picrate, m.p. 232-33° (undepressed by that obtained from fraction B, *cf.* part I *loc. cit.*).

2-Styryl-4-ethyl-6-methylpyridine and its Salts.—The base, regenerated with alkali, was a straw-coloured oily liquid. It was converted into the hydrochloride. The sticky hydrochloride on washing with ether turned into a powder. To the well cooled yellow solution of the hydrochloride in water, a solution of potassium iodide in water was added when the hydroiodide of the monostyryl base came down as a sticky mass which soon turned to a mass of yellow needles. An attempt was made to crystallise the hydroiodide from dilute alcohol but it turned into an oily mass at ordinary temperature. It is soluble in common organic solvents. However, the monostyryl base in ether gave with ethereal hydrogen chloride a sticky hydrochloride. After washing with ether and triturating with a little acetone, it turned into a mass of needles with a pale tinge. It was soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform and water and had m.p. 208°. On drying in *vacuo* it suffered a loss of 32.7%. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 73.8; H, 6.55; N, 5.39. $C_{16}H_{17}N$, HCl requires C, 73.58; H, 7.25; N, 5.37 per cent).

The *hydroiodide*, prepared from the above hydrochloride, was crystallised from alcohol-ether mixture, m.p. 203° . It is soluble in alcohol, chloroform, acetone and water. It lost 4.2% of its weight at 100° in *vacuo*. (Found in dried material : C, 54.34 ; H, 4.90 ; N, 3.58 ; I, 36.95. $C_{16}H_{17}N$, HI requires C, 54.70 ; H, 5.13 ; N, 3.99 ; I, 36.19 per cent).

The *chloroplatinate*, prepared in the usual way, was obtained as an amorphous powder soluble in acetone, chloroform, alcohol and ethyl acetate, m.p. 243° after drying over P_2O_5 . [Found in anhydrous material : C, 45.57 ; H, 4.39 ; N, 3.0 ; Pt, 23.06. $(C_{16}H_{17}N, HCl)_2 \cdot PtCl_4$ requires C, 44.85 ; H, 4.20 ; N, 3.27 ; Pt, 22.8 per cent].

The *aurichloride* was obtained by mixing together aqueous solutions of gold chloride and the hydrochloride as golden yellow mass, m.p. 145° after drying. It is soluble in acetone and chloroform.

The *picrate* crystallised in lemon-yellow tufts of needles from acetone, m.p. 233° (sublimes at 90° in *vacuo*). [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo* : C, 58.63 ; H, 4.52 ; N, 12.35. $C_{16}H_{17}N \cdot C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 58.41 ; H, 4.14 ; N, 12.39 per cent].

2 : 6-Distyryl-4-ethylpyridine and its Salts.

2 : 6-Distyryl-4-ethylpyridine.—The base from hydrochloride "B" dissolved in alcohol was isolated with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and washed with water. Its solution in ether showed a violet fluorescence. The ether solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue from ether was dissolved in petroleum ether and filtered from a negligible quantity of tarry impurities. The light yellow coloured filtrate on keeping at 0° crystallised in bunches of closely packed small needles, m.p. 85° . It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, benzene, ethyl acetate, ether and petroleum ether. At 100° in *vacuo* it lost 2.9% of its weight. (Found in material dried at 60° in *vacuo* : C, 88.19 ; H, 6.7 ; N, 4.53. Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo* : C, 88.63 ; H, 6.95. $C_{23}H_{21}N$ requires C, 88.74 ; H, 6.75 ; N, 4.50 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* "B" crystallised in needles from dilute acetic acid. It may be prepared from the chloroform solution of the base with ethereal hydrogen chloride. On crystallisation from chloroform-alcohol mixture it separated in small light yellow needles, m.p. $271-72^{\circ}$. It is soluble in acetone, chloroform and methyl alcohol and difficultly in ethanol.

The *picrate*, prepared in ether solution, dissolved difficultly in alcohol and on concentrating the alcoholic solution crystallised in prisms, m.p. 255° . It is soluble in acetone. [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo* :

C, 64.58; H, 4.28; N, 10.87. $C_{23}H_{21}N$, $C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 64.44; H, 4.44; N, 10.37 per cent).

Attempted Condensation of 2:6-Distyryl-4-ethylpyridine with Benzaldehyde.—When a mixture of 2:6-distyryl-4-ethylpyridine (1 mol., 6 g.), benzaldehyde (1.5 mol.; 3.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (6 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 15 hours and the product worked out in the usual way only unchanged reactants were isolated in quantitative yield.

Oxidation of 2-Styryl-4-ethyl-6-methylpyridine: Formation of 4-Ethyl-6-methylpyridine-2-(α)-carboxylic Acid.—An ice-cold solution of styryl derivative (10 g.) in acetone (200 c.c.) was oxidised with finely powdered potassium permanganate (2.5 mols., 17 g.) added in portions during an interval of 30 minutes. The reaction mixture was filtered and the precipitate washed with acetone and extracted with hot water. The acetone solution gave some unreacted monostyryl derivative. The aqueous filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated in *vacuo*. The residue dissolved in ether and after removal of the solvent, was taken up in alcohol and an alcoholic solution of lead acetate was added when a little lead salt (0.1 g.) separated which did not melt below 360° . The alcoholic filtrate was evaporated to dryness in *vacuo* and the residue was suspended in water and delead. The clear aqueous filtrate was again evaporated in *vacuo* and the residue was dissolved in petroleum ether and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solution after concentration was kept in ice-chest when some crystalline sediment appeared but it could not be separated and on filtering turned oily.

Decarboxylation of the Above acid.—The above acid was heated with a trace of copper powder when the base distilled with evolution of carbon dioxide.

2-Methyl-4-ethylpyridine Picrate.—The distillate was converted into the picrate as pale yellow needles, in ether solution, m.p. 142° , after washing with ether. It crystallised with $\frac{1}{2}$ mol. water of crystallisation which it lost at 100° in *vacuo*. (Found: H_2O , 3.0. Calc. 2.6 per cent). [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 47.98; H, 3.97; N, 16.47. $C_8H_{11}N \cdot C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 47.99; H, 3.97; N, 16.0 per cent]. The m.p. of 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine picrate as given in literature is 142° . The m.p. of synthetic picrate mixed with the picrate of the base $C_8H_{11}N$ obtained from alkaline degradation of strychnine and brucine, was indefinite ($115-25^\circ$) thereby establishing non-identity.

The analyses were done by micro-method by Dr. Ing. A. Schöller, Berlin.